

THE TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL PRACTICE IN CORPORATE EDUCATION FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF TEACHING KNOWLEDGE

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Abstract

The present article proposes to identify the practical aspects of the teacher's professional activity in Corporate Education that can be improved from reflections based on the Theory of Teaching Knowledge developed by Tardif (2000). For this work, the research method used was the literature review. The research results indicate interdependencies between the need for continued development of the teacher, the dissociation of academic knowledge and the teaching practice in organizations, and knowledge gaps regarding the competencies of the professional who works in Corporate Education. The Theory of Teaching Knowledge opens a discussion on the diversity of existing profiles of professionals working in organizations responsible for transmitting knowledge and training people who can contribute to the sustainability and competitiveness of organizations.

Keywords: Corporate Education; Teaching Knowledge; Teacher's practice.

INTRODUCTION

Within the public and private organizations, educational practices are aimed at articulating organizational strategic objectives to the skills of the individuals who work in them, combining these elements to achieve results related to productivity and the improvement of products and services (CORDEIRO, 2022). This form of mastery of the teaching and learning process in organizations is called Corporate Education, whose success depends not only on the people who learn but also on the people responsible for teaching.

This article deals with the second group of people – the individuals who deal with teaching in the context of Corporate Education. Several theories deal with the forms and tools of learning. However, it must be considered that other theories also address the issue of teaching, providing subsidies for reflections and critical analysis on this topic.

Approaching teaching through the prism of Corporate Education is justified because it is a theme related to the competitiveness and success of organizations, as well as to the development of skills of individuals that can enable favorable results for organizational ventures. Therefore, this approach interests executives, managers, administrators – decision makers in organizations – and individuals who work in the various work groups that constitute such social contexts. Furthermore, this issue is also relevant for researchers whose investigations are related to Corporate Education, Organizational Learning, and Strategic Planning at the organizational level.

Considering the relevance of the proposed theme and considering that there are individuals responsible for planning, developing, evaluating, and implementing improvements and adjustments whenever possible/necessary in Corporate Education practices, this work is dedicated to investigating aspects of the role of the professional responsible for teaching. – named for this investigation as a trainer – based on a theory that, although not explicitly developed for Corporate Education, can provide subsidies for a discussion based on the research question.

The research problem that makes the present study possible is the following: What practical aspects of the professional activity of the trainer in Corporate Education can be improved from reflections based on the Theory of Teaching Knowledge?

Even if Tardif's Theory of Teaching Knowledge (2000) has not explicitly been elaborated to reflect on the teacher's teaching practice in Corporate Education, the proposition

examined through this study, can provide a theoretical basis applicable to the activities developed by this class of professionals in the context of the educational modality. Research objectives were established to answer the research problem and verify the initial proposition.

The general objective of the research is to identify the practical aspects of the professional activity of the trainer in Corporate Education that can be improved from reflections based on the Theory of Teaching Knowledge. Achieve the specific objectives were also defined, namely: addressing the legal aspects related to the professional activity of the trainer in Corporate Education; presenting the different nomenclatures related to the trainer in Corporate Education; identifying the characteristics of the trainer in Corporate Education relevant in the context of organizations and establish relationships between the information emerging from the research. The research objectives listed demanded the choice of a research method suitable for the proposed work.

The research method adopted for this scientific article was the literature review. It will be detailed in the next section of the work. After exposing the method, the research results will be presented in the form of a theoretical basis, the discussions of emerging information, the relationships built through the investigation, and the final considerations regarding the work carried out. The following section explains how the research was carried out and its main characteristics.

2 THEORETICAL REFERENCE

Other names also known as Corporate Education (CE); for example, education in companies is defined as a set of practices that integrate people and knowledge management (CORDEIRO, 2022). Additionally, CE is related to actions aimed at professional improvement, increasing skills, and cognitive understanding (SECURATO, 2019).

Historically, education related to professional development was conceived as an inferior practice and stigmatized by the fact that the first apprentices were forestry, orphans, and enslaved people, with activities linked to strictly manual work. This craft and learning were a punishment, not a form of development. The professional activity considered superior, intellectually elevated, and noble was restricted to medical, law,

and engineering training intended for privileged members of society (SECURATO, 2019).

Still considering the historical context, Corporate Universities (CU) emerged approximately in 1960 in the company General Electric (GE). The CU structures were designed to address current demands in companies, both in developing relevant/required technical skills and managing the organization's culture (SECURATO, 2019).

Correlating this historical aspect with what is observed today, GE can also be a reference for effectiveness in the CE theme. The GE company continues to make robust investments in its UC, Crotonville, which works to train employees and disseminate the organization's culture and values (EBOLI, 2016). This purpose is still in line with the one that historically motivated the creation of CUs in organizations.

When approaching the presence of PAs in Brazil, it is possible to notice that these structures are increasingly relevant in the entire business environment. This increase is justified by the need for constant improvement, considering various spheres of knowledge (e.g., human behavior and technology), and by the reputational improvement that can be promoted by the CUs and perceived internally and externally (SILVA et al., 2017). Thus, it is possible to connect CE with what Tardif (2000) points out about teaching knowledge manifested in educational initiatives: programs, collective practices, disciplines, and others. For this, this work discusses aspects that characterize the role of the teacher in CE.

2.1 The Corporative Education Professional

Professionals who work in organizations have attributions related to their work activities. When dealing with those responsible for teaching in the context of CE, it was initially decided to call them trainers. However, several denominations can be used to refer to them. In this regard, here are some considerations.

2.1.1 The CE professional's nomenclatures

When referring to the professional who works in the CE and the professional as an educator, it is possible to find numerous denominations, some of them being monitor, tutor, mentor, and teacher-tutor. However, the use of these terms is not restricted to CE and may have different specifications. Some definitions that contribute to understanding each of these nomenclatures are shown in Chart 1:

chart 1 – Examples of nomenclature related to the professional educator in CE.

Autor	Nomenclature	Definition
Houaiss (2007)	Monitor	An advanced student who has the role of a teacher. The instructor's assistant accompanies or guides students or interns in executing a task.
Botti and Rego (2008)	Tutor	A teacher dedicated to teaching the student to "learn to learn." In this scenario, the tutor is considered a guide, a facilitator who assists in the student-centered learning process.
	Mentor	Professional with more experience also monitors and advises other professionals who are starting their careers. To support the student's teaching and learning process, the mentor acts as an essential enabler of the personal and professional growth of the professionals he mentors.
Garcia and Silva (2017)	Professor-tutor	In addition to the pedagogical purpose, the teacher-tutor has a role linked to student motivation in general and related to the challenges of virtual learning, seeking to solve even technical problems.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

The sample presented in Chart 1 does not represent the totality of nomenclatures used to refer to the professional who works as an educator in the CE. However, it already provides recurrent and recognizable terms in the corporate environment. In addition to dealing with nominations, it is possible to address the attributes related to these professionals from a case study that can contextualize the object of this study.

2.1.2 Case study: *The characteristics of the CE Professional*

CE practice is not restricted to the academic environment. It is designed according to the trainer's experience in their performance in the organization. Pereira (2022) carried out a case study from the faculty of a European multinational company that has been providing EC solutions in Brazil for over 40 years.

As for the academic training of teachers, the results of the survey by Pereira (2022) indicate that 100% of the respondents had a college degree; 43% had a specific course in Education field; 86% had a postgraduate course (specialization); 37% had a master's degree, and none of the interviewees had a doctorate.

Considering the professional experience of the participants of the case study in question, most had more than ten years of experience as EC teachers (76%). Many of them had no experience with conducting classes in the online format in the period before the COVID-19 pandemic (65%), and 67% reported having difficulties adapting to new technologies, considering that the use of distance learning technologies became to be part of the essential curriculum of these professionals (PEREIRA, 2022).

In the case study on screen, it appears that most professionals working as teachers do not have education training, being trained in the organizational environment itself, from the practices inherent to their work area. It is precisely on the teaching practice and activities of the teaching profession that this work seeks to reflect from a theory that, although not explicitly designed for CE, can provide subsidies to fill the gaps related to training trainers.

2.3 The Teaching Knowledge Theory

Tardif (2000) developed an epistemological view of teachers' professional practice, emphasizing teaching work. To understand the professionalization of teaching and teachers, he dedicated his research to teacher training, seeking to address the various types of knowledge that constitute the activity of the teaching profession, intending to emphasize the fundamental characteristics of the teaching profession. For this, it discussed educational practices and approached the teacher from different points of view, among which the "investigative, reflective, political, dialogic, intellectual" teacher can be identified (RIBEIRO; GONÇALVES, 2018, p. 992).

Since the teacher is a professional capable of mediating the teaching and learning process in specific situations, it can be said that this professional promotes the confluence of shared meanings. Teaching consists of a process endowed with intentions and takes place in the interaction between people. Verbal communication and dialogic speech are intrinsically related to teaching, as they are means used to make learning possible in specific contexts. The act of teaching aims at learning, without which there is no teaching (RIBEIRO; GONÇALVES, 2018). In this way, the teacher's mediation and communication make learning possible. This professional is responsible for the interactive activity of the didactic practices and managing the conditions under which people learn.

Given the undeniable importance of teachers for learning development and considering everything that is demanded of these professionals, it is necessary to reflect on how the educational area is prepared for their professionalization in general. The professionalization of teaching establishes a field of convergence for political decisions in education, reforms of teaching institutions, and new sets of ideas about the training of teaching professionals and about teaching itself (TARDIF, 2000). It is precisely at the heart of these converging forces that the epistemology of professional practice and teaching knowledge is questioned.

The teacher's skills, understandings, knowledge, and dispositions make up his knowledge base to teach and promote learning at different levels, fields of knowledge, and teaching modalities (RIBEIRO; GONÇALVES, 2018). In the initial training of teachers, this base is more limited, and it becomes more profound, more manageable, diverse, and comprehensive throughout their professional practice. Throughout this experience, the teacher must rely on specialized and formalized knowledge, through scientific disciplines in a broad sense, acquired during training of a university nature (or that produces the same effects as this). Based on these subjects, the teacher's professional knowledge can be used to solve concrete problems and situations in which this knowledge becomes endowed with practical value (TARDIF, 2000).

This contextualized and resolute application of the teacher's knowledge gives the competence and the prerogative to use the knowledge in didactic practices. That means only professionals with adequate training for teaching can master such knowledge and adequately apply their knowledge from the practice of teaching, with the capacity to

consciously evaluate the learning of the subjects and the results of the work of their peers (TARDIF, 2000). From this perspective, the knowledge, the know-how, and the know-how of the teacher gain relevance.

From the theoretical point of view of Tardif (2000), teacher knowledge is present in social reality, made up of elements such as training, programs, collective practices, disciplines, and more. These elements configure the teaching knowledge, situated between the individual and social spheres (teacher and the system in which he works, respectively) through six "conducting threads" (RIBEIRO; GONÇALVES, 2018, p. 1000), defined as follows: knowledge and job; diversity of knowledge; temporality of knowledge; work experience as a foundation of knowledge; human knowledge about human beings; and knowledge and teacher training.

Knowledge and work are terms that relate to how the teacher's knowledge needs to be contextualized in the professional environment, given that the relationships articulated by work contribute to the confrontation and solution of situations experienced in the didactic environment (RIBEIRO; GONÇALVES, 2018). The teacher's knowledge gives him autonomy and discernment, as well as a considerable amount of improvisation to unusual and unique situations, which end up demanding from the professional the understanding of problems, the organization, clarification of intended objectives, and the identification of means to be used to achieve such goals (TARDIF, 2000).

The diversity of knowledge reveals that teaching knowledge is plural. The teacher's family, the school where the professional studied, his culture, the institutions in which he worked, as well as his relationship with his peers, and the training courses he took, in short, all these sources give the teacher a pluralism of knowledge (RIBEIRO; GONÇALVES, 2018). The typological model proposed by Tardif (2012) considers that the teacher's professional development is associated with social sources and the places where the professional acquired his knowledge, allowing him to integrate this knowledge into his teaching work. For example, textbooks and qualification programs can be social sources of knowledge acquisition, which teachers can practically integrate into their teaching work.

The temporality of knowledge demonstrates that the diversified knowledge of the teacher is also temporal, as its acquisition occurs in the period of the professional's life history (RIBEIRO; GONÇALVES, 2018). This teaching knowledge makes it possible to

understand that progressive action is necessary for the teacher to learn to teach. In this regard, it is essential to highlight that "Both in its theoretical bases and its practical consequences, professional knowledge is evolutionary and progressive and therefore requires continuous and continuous training" (TARDIF, 2000, p. 7). The gradual increase in teaching knowledge is, therefore, directly related to the work experience of this professional.

When approaching work experience as a foundation of knowledge, Tardif (2012) clarifies that teaching knowledge originated through work experience forms the basis of the practice and competencies on which the teacher sustains the teaching activity, using diverse knowledge that can be transformed and adapted for/by the teaching work. Therefore, it is necessary to consider how the teacher develops didactic practices in didactic environments, i.e., how the teacher concretely integrates their knowledge in their professional tasks (RIBEIRO; GONÇALVES, 2018), which seeks to encourage people's learning.

Teaching knowledge is made up of human knowledge about human beings. This notion denotes the interactive character of teaching work since the teacher relates to his work object through human interaction (RIBEIRO; GONÇALVES, 2018). The knowledge, strategies, and techniques employed in concrete situations reveal the teacher's professional expertise. It implies that teaching knowledge is socially and locally constructed, endowed with ethical instances intrinsic to professional performance applied to human beings (TARDIF, 2000). This reflection on the teaching profession also gives space for consideration of the training of professionals for work.

When dealing with knowledge and teacher training, Tardif (2012) considered that knowledge is the result of other previous knowledge, and this denotes the need for reflections on teacher training and the specifics of this professional's daily work. There is professional knowledge that teachers effectively use in their daily activities, both to perform tasks and to achieve specific goals. Much of this professional knowledge differs from university knowledge derived from research in educational sciences and the knowledge present in university training courses for future teachers (TARDIF, 2000). Thus, the professionalization of teaching and teacher training are areas that need to articulate the teaching knowledge of the professional, the university knowledge of the trainers, and the researchers' scientific knowledge.

The coherent amalgam established by the set of teaching knowledge from different sources brings together four other types of knowledge typologically classified (TARDIF, 2012): knowledge from professional training, disciplinary knowledge, curricular knowledge, and experiential knowledge. Chart 2 presents this typology of knowledge:

Chart 2 - Typological classification of teaching knowledge.

Type of knowledge	Description
The teacher education knowledge	Set of knowledge transmitted by the institutions of teacher education (e.g., faculties), which concentrate the confluence of other knowledge from society, school institutions, trainers, researchers, and others.
The disciplinary knowledge	Knowledge corresponding to the different fields of knowledge available to society, integrated into universities, within the faculties in the form of subjects (e.g., Portuguese, mathematics, history, and others). They are emerging products from the cultural tradition and the activity of the social groups that produce knowledge.
The curriculum knowledge	Knowledge related to discourses, objectives, contents, and methods, which the school institution categorizes and selects in order to serve as a model of literary culture. Its implementation takes place through school programs teachers must learn and apply.
Experiential knowledge	Configured in the daily exercise of the profession. They are incorporated into individual and collective experience in the form of habits, i.e., dispositions acquired in/by actual practice, which allow the teacher to face the conditioning factors of his profession.

Source: prepared by the authors, adapted from Tardif (2012) and Ribeiro and Gonçalves (2018).

Chart 2 shows that teaching knowledge can result in habits that constitute authentic teaching styles, riddled with tricks, resources, tricks, and the teacher's personal touches. These habits are manifested through know-how and personal and professional know-how, which will be legitimized by the daily work of teaching (TARDIF, 2012). This knowledge used by the teacher in the context of the profession and the didactic environment is not elaborated directly by the teachers themselves since many of them are extrinsic to the teaching process and originate in different social places of the teaching career. Some are outside the teaching profession, of the teacher's daily activities. Therefore, professional knowledge is found at the convergence of different

points of knowledge, such as society, the life history of the individual, the history of school institutions, the production of trainers and researchers, and other sources (RIBEIRO; GONÇALVES, 2018).

The similar aspects of the different teaching knowledge reveal Tardif's perspective on the inseparability between theory and practice in teacher training and between training and teaching work (RIBEIRO; GONÇALVES, 2018). The epistemology of professional practice is the study of the knowledge employed by teachers in their common workspaces to perform their tasks (TARDIF, 2000). This epistemological study aims to reveal teaching knowledge, understand how they are integrated into teaching tasks and how subjects can incorporate, produce, apply, and even transform this knowledge, considering the limits and resources related to their attributions. Regarding this variety of knowledge, it is essential to note that:

Professional knowledge is also varied and heterogeneous because it does not form a unified repertoire of knowledge, for example, around a discipline, a technology, or a teaching concept; they are rather eclectic and syncretic (TARDIF, 2000, p. 14).

This epistemology of the teacher's professional practice contributes to CE by renewing the foundations by which knowledge about the teaching process is produced. A careful examination of this process provides elements that enable reflection on the teacher's practice, thus promoting the relevance of the role of those responsible for teaching and work situations in organizations, considering the knowledge mobilized so that these practices achieve objectives and results defined in the organizational strategic planning.

Therefore, the Theory of Teaching Knowledge seeks to address teaching professionals' activity, emphasizing the teaching profession's fundamental characteristics. Having presented the theoretical basis is opportune to promote the discussion of emerging information through research.

3 METHOD

The research that enabled the production of this scientific article was developed from a descriptive literature review. This method enables the summary of prior knowledge on a given topic. It can be used to determine the extent to which studies in a research area reveal the structures and trends related to propositions, theories, or discoveries (PARÉ et al., 2015).

The practical aspects of the trainer in Corporate Education were demanded to select bibliographic sources. That could provide theoretical subsidies to address a researchable topic, following the objectives of the proposed investigation, so that relations and reflections could be

established and discussed under the perspective of the formulated research problem, pointing to the possibility of future research related to the delimited theme (CRESWELL, 2007).

Thus, the research carried out is characterized by a qualitative approach, with the purpose of understanding and deepening the understanding of a phenomenon (the trainer's professional activity) explored from the perspective of an environment and concerning a defined context (the development of people and organizations), with an investigation process developed through problem formulation, literature review, the emergence of proposition and immersion in the field of knowledge of Corporate Education (SAMPIERI; COLLADO; LUCIO, 2013).

Having presented the research method, the next section of this work is dedicated to the theoretical framework that provided the basis for the work developed.

4 DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The Theory of Teaching Knowledge emphasizes the fundamental characteristics of the teaching profession. According to the study carried out by PEREIRA (2022), this characterization of the CE professional's performance is still conditioned on a specific analysis of the corporate scenario of this professional's performance. Practical knowledge is acquired in the professional's performance, which can make the knowledge acquired in the academic environment obsolete or not applicable to the corporate context.

Considering the concepts of the CE by Cordeiro (2022), the historical aspects addressed by Securato (2019), the findings of Pereira (2022), and the theoretical perspective elaborated by Tardif (2000), it is possible to identify connections and interdependencies between them. Given the progressive deepening, it is possible to make numerous considerations about the inseparability of theory and practice (TARDIF, 2000; PEREIRA; 2022). In addition, CE aims to improve skills and knowledge essential to consolidate the organizational culture, meaning progressive and continuous work (SECURATO, 2019; CORDEIRO, 2022).

As shown, the EC teaching practice nomenclatures (Chart 1) design significant correlations between the descriptions presented and the EC professionals' activities. The association with the term "tutor" is correlated to the act of teaching someone in "learn to learn" (BOTTI and REGO, 2008). It means to allow the apprentice to learn to

deal with unusual situations, understand and solve problems, as well as identify ways to achieve specific goals (TARDIF, 2000) within organizations.

When it comes to the mentor's practice, and in addition to the teaching and learning objective, he also follows the career of the professional to whom they mentor, being able to provide counseling and having a concern related to their growth (and not only to the improvement of skills) (BOTTI and REGO, 2008). It connects with other areas of the organization, such as Human Resources, and, simultaneously, is a critical element for organizational learning. Knowledge from experience is a fundamental characteristic of the teacher's competence (TARDIF, 2000). This tacit knowledge makes the trainer's experience an integral part of the student's education, and this knowledge is incorporated individually and collectively in the form of habits.

The role of "tutor-teacher" has a slightly more restricted scope compared to that of a mentor but has responsibilities beyond the pedagogical ones and can also encourage the student in the learning environment, with a unique role in virtual environments, which require operational and often technical support (GARCIA and SILVA, 2017). The teachers themselves presented the necessary improvisations to face situations and problems in the pandemic scenario, which required the acquisition of new skills, such as the use of technological tools for the operation of learning management systems (PEREIRA, 2022). In this sense, the pandemic scenario allowed professionals with the assignment of teacher-tutor to have outstanding importance.

Articulation between teachers' university education and teaching professionalization is necessary. Academic training knowledge, disciplinary knowledge, curriculum knowledge, and experience knowledge form the habits that will constitute the teaching style - the know-how and personal and professional know-how present in the trainer's practice (TARDIF, 2000). The case study presented an illustrative way for this investigation (an organization whose business model aims at CE) to expose the situation of a group of teachers who, for the most part, did not have specific education training, drawing attention to the need for teaching experience (PEREIRA, 2022). The need to update this knowledge enables the continuous and sustainable performance of teaching activities through adaptation to new scenarios.

Within the scope of CE, the acquisition of teaching skills is conditioned by the trainer's role in the organization. The practices of this teaching modality can corroborate the

development of the people who learn and those responsible for teaching, allowing this practical experience, combined with academic training, to face challenging issues emerging from their profession.

5 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The Corporate Education theme opens the field for essential discussions about its conceptualization. It is structuring as a process, its delimitation as a practice, and its contribution to the formation of competencies that help organizations remain competitive in the market where they operate. Given the existence of several theoretical lines and their possible practical applications for organizations, this article stimulated reflections on the characteristics of the trainer in Corporate Education in the light of Tardif's Theory of Teaching Knowledge (2000).

The trainer profile in Corporate Education presents characteristics acquired during the teaching experience (even if this professional is not a teacher). It is aligned with his academic training and his practical teaching performance in organizations, influenced by business models and organizational cultures, resulting in the acquisition of multiple pieces of knowledge.

This multiplicity of knowledge resulting from the intersection between the history of individuals, educational institutions, and the curricular scope in the training process of trainers and researchers and the practice in organizations gives rise to a very peculiar professional in Corporate Education, without a single curricular competence. And delimited. A gap in the professional profile of the trainer in Corporate Education may result from their academic training, which does not give them sufficient skills to meet organizational demands. In organizations, filling this gap in teaching knowledge is a work in progress, given that the corporate environment demands teaching skills to deal with ever-changing scenarios.

Therefore, the practical application proposed in this work, based on the articulation between the Teaching Knowledge and the professional activity of the trainers in Corporate Education, can enable professionals working as teachers to reformulate their approaches in the face of constant organizational changes and can help those entering this field. Field of work to prepare to deal with the challenges they will face to develop their personal and professional know-how and know-how.

This work presents the possibility of new research, promoting dialogues that combine theory and practice for improvement and self-management of the trainer's careers in Corporate Education, as well as to develop studies on the effectiveness of the performance of these professionals in the face of the strategic vision of the organizations.

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